

Trust Score Prediction and Management in IoT Ecosystems Using Markov Chains and MADM Techniques

Michail Bampatsikos¹, Ilias Politis², Thodoris Ioannidis¹ and Christos Xenakis¹

¹Systems Security Laboratory, University of Piraeus, Greece
 {mbampatsikos, th.ioannidis,xenakis}@ssl-unipi.gr

²Industrial Systems Institute / Research Center "Athena", Patras, Greece
 politis@athenarc.gr

Abstract—The growth of IoT networks necessitates robust and adaptive trust management (TM) systems to ensure secure and reliable interactions between devices. This paper introduces a novel TM framework for IoT devices, leveraging a statistical Markov chain model to calculate dynamic trust scores. Our approach integrates a Multi-Attribute Decision-Making (MADM) methodology to rank devices based on trustworthiness, providing a resource-efficient alternative to machine learning (ML)-based models. In contrast to ML approaches, which often require extensive data and are vulnerable to adversarial attacks, our statistical model provides a resilient and computationally efficient solution suitable for environments with limited data availability. The system architecture combines a Trust Management Server (TMS), an Intrusion Detection System (IDS), and Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) to secure data integrity and enable real-time trust assessment. Performance evaluations confirm the model's capacity to manage diverse security threats within IoT ecosystems, while future work will focus on enhancing the system's adaptability to novel threats, such as zero-day attacks, and exploring alternative decision-making models to improve resilience under uncertainty. This TM approach advances IoT network security by offering a scalable, lightweight solution adaptable to varied IoT environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystems is reshaping key industries, including transportation, healthcare, agriculture, energy, and smart cities [1] [2] [3] [4]. As IoT systems become integral to critical infrastructure, ensuring their trustworthiness has become a major challenge. IoT ecosystems are inherently heterogeneous, with devices having different security capabilities, hardware and software configurations. This complexity makes it difficult to apply a standardised security framework across these systems, creating an urgent need for robust Trust Management (TM) mechanisms that ensure the reliable operation of devices in dynamic environments. The diversity of devices introduces vulnerabilities and trust issues, with device security, reliability and performance being critical factors in maintaining network integrity.

One of the key challenges in IoT networks is quantifying and managing trust between devices. Unlike human actors, IoT devices cannot make nuanced decisions about trust, requiring

a quantifiable and actionable system for establishing trust relationships. Trust needs to be measured and expressed in a way that is understandable to both the system and its human operators. Current methods for assessing trust often focus on narrow aspects, such as security or privacy, without considering the full range of factors that affect trust in IoT environments. These challenges highlight the importance of developing a comprehensive TM framework that can adapt to the diverse conditions found in IoT networks.

This paper presents a novel Trust Management (TM) approach designed to bridge existing gaps by offering a flexible framework for trust evaluation in IoT environments. The framework computes a device's trust score using a two-dimensional Markov chain model, considering both contextual factors and service requirements. Additionally, a Multi-Attribute Decision-Making (MADM) methodology ranks devices based on their trustworthiness. A key innovation in this work is the use of Markov chains to predict the evolution of a device's trust score over time, enabling more precise forecasts of future performance and reliability. This prediction technique is especially valuable in data-scarce environments, where traditional machine-learning methods are less effective. By leveraging a statistical model, the framework provides accurate predictions with minimal data, making it particularly suited for resource-constrained IoT systems.

The contributions of this paper are twofold: first, the introduction of a piecewise function for calculating lifecycle-based trust scores, and second, the application of Markov chains to predict trust score trajectories. Furthermore, the integration of the TOPSIS method within the MADM framework enhances device ranking accuracy, which is crucial for selecting the most reliable devices in IoT ecosystems. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time these techniques have been applied in the context of IoT trust management, underscoring the originality of our approach. Moreover, the model includes key parameters whose tuning affects trust score calculations, highlighting the need to balance security and operational metrics. Initial sensitivity analysis on these parameters is discussed in Section IV to illustrate the model's robustness under varying configurations.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section II provides a concise overview of the current literature of trust management and calculation of trust score over IoT, while Section III defines the proposed mathematical framework for the dynamic trusts score calculation. A comprehensive performance evaluation of the efficiency of the mathematical model and its comparison over real-world simulation scenarios is provided in Section IV, while a security analysis of the proposed TM is discussed in Section V. The paper is concluded in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

This literature review examines significant studies in TM within IoT networks, with a focus on device-related criteria such as Quality of Service, Delays, and service feedback. The goal is to identify and critique the key methodologies for calculating a device's trust score. The review is divided into two categories: Blockchain-based and non-blockchain TM approaches.

A. Blockchain-based Trust Management

The authors of [5] propose a blockchain-based method to determine the trustworthiness of IoT devices in supply chains. Their framework considers both Direct Trust (DT) and Indirect Trust (IT), where DT is derived from direct interactions between IoT nodes, and IT is based on information from third-party nodes (e.g., recommendations). Trustworthiness is calculated using historical feedback and recommendations as key parameters. Similarly, [6] presents a scalable blockchain-based solution for key management and TM in IoT networks, where the trust score is based on a device's historical reputation and feedback from its services. In [7], the authors present a blockchain-based TM model for Vehicular Ad-hoc Networks (VANETs) using Hyperledger Fabric. The trust score calculation, which considers the historical behavior of vehicles and message authenticity, is performed using a Hidden Markov Model. A different study [8] talks about a blockchain-based TM model for agricultural supply chains. It uses a game theory model based on the Bayesian formula, and trust scores are calculated by counting the number of positive and negative feedbacks.

In [9], a blockchain-based TM mechanism for smart buildings is proposed, where trustworthiness is computed as a weighted sum of past and current trust values. The approach in [10] integrates blockchain technology and fog computing to focus on TM in IoT. This methodology uses three parameters: the trust of the SR to the SP for a specific service, direct observations by the SR, and recommendations from other nodes. Another study [11] describes a blockchain-based TM model that calculates trust scores on the fly by combining DT and IT data and using a trust value decay function and weights that can be changed.

A DLT-based identity and trust framework for IoT devices is proposed in [12], where trust relationships between nodes are represented as graph edges, forming a web of trust. In [13], a TM methodology is introduced that calculates an IoT device's initial trust score using a weighted sum of

factors such as remote attestation outcomes, device ownership, application context, and the presence of TPM, TEE, or SGX. Another blockchain-based approach [14] employs an alliance blockchain to compute a device's trust score through a weighted sum function considering reputation and other feature scores in supply chains. The work in [15] utilizes a MADM methodology, considering factors like Cyber Risk, Ease of Access, and security standing, and integrates Hyperledger Fabric DLT. A TM mechanism for the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) using blockchain technology is presented in [16], which evaluates trustworthiness based on successful and failed transactions, transaction history, and risk factors. The authors of [17] propose a privacy-preserving TM architecture for the Industrial IoT, incorporating a federated learning trust model. The trust evaluation process involves collecting trust data and calculating a node's trustworthiness using a weighted sum equation, with weights derived from federated learning.

B. Non-Blockchain-based Trust Management

The TM mechanism proposed in [18] computes an IoT device's trust score using a function that considers the device's Quality of Service, Availability, Cruciality, Responsiveness, and Cooperation. A Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) method and a Deep Long Short-Term Memory method are used in [19] to figure out trust scores based on factors like packet loss, delay, and throughput, with Shannon's entropy function used to decide the weights. A context-dependent TM method is suggested in [20] for choosing and assigning tasks in a social IoT environment. Trust scores are found by adding up factors like device capabilities, task commitment, and service consumer satisfaction.

The TM approach presented in [21] for large-scale IoT networks treats the network as a graph representing trust relationships between devices. These relationships, which can be either trustworthy or untrustworthy, are formed using a random-walk network exploration algorithm. An edge-based TM system for smart cities, using Eigenvector analysis, is proposed in [22], where both DT and IT are calculated based on events associated with the devices. The EdgeTrust model introduced in [23] addresses good-mouthing and bad-mouthing attacks, computing trust scores as a sum of DT, IT, and past experience. A hybrid TM scheme for the Internet of Vehicles (IoV) is proposed in [24], where trust is evaluated in two steps: assessing the authenticity of information and the validity of the information itself. The scheme in [25] combines Bayesian learning and Dempster-Shafer Theory (DST) to compute trust in IoT devices, focusing on both entity and data trustworthiness.

C. Comments on the Reviewed Related Work

Among the works reviewed, only [13] and [15] address the issue of initial trust score calculation. However, the parameters used in [13] are not strongly indicative of a device's trustworthiness, and the approach does not compute trust scores

throughout the device's lifecycle. While [15] considers trust-related parameters for initial and updated trust score calculations, it has limitations: it cannot predict future trustworthiness and does not account for feedback from other devices (i.e., reputation) in the network. Furthermore, most reviewed works do not perform MADM-based trust evaluation using a combination of network and device-related parameters. The exception still does not consider expert subjective preferences, which are crucial as the importance of a parameter can vary across different services, impacting trust evaluation.

In addition to our current methodology, alternative decision-making frameworks like fuzzy logic and Bayesian inference offer robust mechanisms for handling uncertainty in IoT trust management. Fuzzy logic [26] allows for a graded approach to trust assessments, accommodating a spectrum of trust levels rather than binary outcomes. Bayesian inference [27], on the other hand, provides a probabilistic foundation for updating trust assessments as new data becomes available. Although our model focuses on computational efficiency through a piecewise function and Markov chains, exploring these alternative frameworks in future work could enhance flexibility and resilience in managing uncertain trust parameters.

III. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF TRUST SCORE CALCULATION

This section presents a comprehensive mathematical framework for the dynamic calculation of trust scores in IoT devices. The proposed model integrates various components crucial to the security and reliability of IoT networks, namely risk assessment, reputation management, and Intrusion Detection System (IDS) scores. The trust score is designed to adapt to evolving security conditions and threats, providing a robust mechanism for real-time trust evaluation in heterogeneous IoT environments.

A. Modeling the Risk

In the context of IoT devices, risk refers to the potential exposure to security threats and vulnerabilities that can compromise the system's integrity, confidentiality and availability. It quantifies the likelihood of security breaches or compromises occurring due to various factors, such as newly discovered vulnerabilities, existing security flaws, and the overall security posture of the device.

The risk state of an IoT device is modeled using a discrete-time Markov chain. This probabilistic approach allows for the representation of transitions between different risk states over time, capturing the dynamic nature of security threats and their impact on the device's risk profile. They are defined as discrete levels, representing varying degrees of security exposure. Each state $\{S_1: \text{Very Low Risk}; S_2: \text{Low Risk}; S_3: \text{Moderate Risk}; S_4: \text{High Risk}; S_5: \text{Very High Risk}\}$ corresponds to a specific level of risk.

1) *Risk Transition Probability*: The transitions between risk states are governed by a transition probability matrix P_R . This matrix captures the likelihood of moving from one risk state to

another in a given time step. The elements of P_R are defined as follows:

$$P_R = \begin{bmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} & \cdots & p_{15} \\ p_{21} & p_{22} & \cdots & p_{25} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ p_{51} & p_{52} & \cdots & p_{55} \end{bmatrix}$$

where p_{ij} represents the probability of transitioning from risk state S_i to risk state S_j . These probabilities are influenced by factors, such as the rate of new vulnerabilities λ and the current vulnerability index V .

2) *Introducing Vulnerability*: The vulnerability index V quantifies the susceptibility of the IoT device to security threats. It is a composite measure that reflects the cumulative effect of known and newly discovered vulnerabilities on the device's risk profile.

a) *Mathematical Representation of V* :

$$V_{t+1} = V_t + \delta V$$

where V_t is the vulnerability index at time t and δV represents the change in the vulnerability index due to new vulnerabilities or security updates.

b) *Change in Vulnerability Index δV* :

$$\delta V = \begin{cases} +0.1 & \text{with probability } p \\ -0.1 & \text{with probability } 1 - p \end{cases}$$

where p is the probability of an increase in the vulnerability index.

The vulnerability index is updated periodically to reflect changes in the device's security environment. A higher V indicates a greater exposure to vulnerabilities, thereby increasing the risk.

3) *Dynamic Update of the Transition Matrix*: The transition matrix P_R is dynamically updated to reflect the changing security conditions of the IoT device. The update function $f(P_R, \lambda, V)$ adjusts the transition probabilities based on the current rate of new vulnerabilities and the vulnerability index. This ensures that the risk state transitions remain responsive to real-time security events. The update function is defined as:

$$P_{R'_{ij}} = \frac{P_{R_{ij}} \cdot (1 - e^{-\lambda} + V)}{\sum_{j=1}^n (P_{R_{ij}} \cdot (1 - e^{-\lambda} + V))}$$

$P_{R'_{ij}}$ is a normalised weighted adjustment function. It adjusts the original transition probabilities by a factor influenced by vulnerability dynamics. Specifically, it performs the following:

Exponential Decay for New Vulnerabilities: The term $1 - e^{-\lambda}$ represents the probability of new vulnerabilities emerging, modeled as an exponential decay function. This term increases with higher values of λ , reflecting a higher probability of encountering new vulnerabilities over time.

Linear Addition of Vulnerability Index: The vulnerability index V is added directly to this adjustment, indicating a linear increase in risk transition probabilities as the device becomes more vulnerable.

Normalization: The transition probabilities are then normalized to ensure that the rows of the transition matrix sum to 1, which is a requirement for valid probability distributions in Markov chains.

4) *Modeling the Impact of V on Risk Transition:* The impact of the vulnerability index V on the risk transition probabilities can be represented as an adjustment factor that modifies the elements of the transition matrix P_R . The function f takes into account the influence of V as follows:

$$P_{R'_{ij}} = P_{R_{ij}} \cdot (1 + \alpha V)$$

where α is a sensitivity parameter that determines the extent to which V affects the transition probabilities and $P_{R'_{ij}}$ is the adjusted transition probability from state S_i to state S_j after considering V . As V increases, the probability of transitioning to higher risk states S_j increases.

The risk transition probabilities are conditional because they depend on the current state. The probability of transitioning to a new risk state R_{t+1} given the current risk state R_t and the influence of λ and V can be expressed as:

$$P(R_{t+1} = S_j | R_t = S_i, \lambda, V) = P_{R'_{ij}}$$

5) *Risk Transition Dynamics:* To comprehend the functioning of the model, it is possible to describe the dynamics of the risk state transitions using the following process:

- 1) **Initialization:** At the beginning of each time step, the current risk state R_t is determined based on the previous state and the transition probabilities in P_R .
- 2) **State Transition:** The transition to the next risk state R_{t+1} is computed using the transition matrix P_R . The probability of transitioning from the current state S_i to the next state S_j is given by p_{ij} .
- 3) **Update Mechanism:** The transition probabilities are updated periodically to account for changes in λ and V . This ensures that the risk model accurately reflects the evolving security landscape.
- 4) **Probability Adjustment:** The transition probabilities are adjusted based on the observed rate of new vulnerabilities and the vulnerability index. For instance, an increase in λ or V would result in higher probabilities of transitioning to higher-risk states.

The probability of being in a particular risk state at time t , given the initial state distribution and the transition matrix, can be represented as:

$$\mathbf{R}(t) = \mathbf{R}(0)P_R^t$$

where $\mathbf{R}(t)$ is the vector of probabilities of being in each risk state at time t , $\mathbf{R}(0)$ is the initial state distribution vector and P_R^t denotes the transition matrix raised to the power of t , representing t steps of state transitions.

B. Modeling the Reputation

In the context of the IoT, reputation can be defined as a measure of the reliability and trustworthiness of a device based on its historical behavior and interactions within the network. The reputation of an IoT device is contingent upon its risk state. Consequently, a higher risk often results in a decline in reputation due to the perception of insecurity and potential threats. Conversely, a lower-risk state can enhance the reputation of a device, thereby signaling its reliability and security to other entities in the network.

The reputation state of an IoT device is modeled using a discrete-time Markov chain, which is analogous to the risk state model. This approach permits the representation of transitions between disparate reputation states over time, which are influenced by the prevailing risk state. The reputation states are represented by the set of discrete levels representing varying degrees of trustworthiness: $\{S_1$: Very Low Reputation; S_2 : Low Reputation; S_3 : Moderate Reputation; S_4 : High Reputation; S_5 : Very High Reputation $\}$.

1) *Transition Probability Matrix P_{Rep} :* The transitions between reputation states are governed by a transition probability matrix P_{Rep} . This matrix captures the likelihood of moving from one reputation state to another in a given time step, influenced by the current risk state.

$$P_{Rep} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & \cdots & r_{15} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & \cdots & r_{25} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{51} & r_{52} & \cdots & r_{55} \end{bmatrix}$$

where r_{ij} represents the probability of transitioning from reputation state S_i to reputation state S_j .

2) *Dynamic Update of the Transition Matrix:* The transition matrix P_{Rep} is dynamically updated based on the current risk state R_t . The function $g(P_{Rep}, R_t)$ adjusts the transition probabilities to reflect the influence of the risk state on the reputation state transitions. This dynamic adjustment ensures that the reputation assessment accurately incorporates the security readiness of the device. The updated transition matrix P'_{Rep} can be expressed as:

$$P'_{Rep} = g(P_{Rep}, R_t)$$

where R_t is the current risk state of the device. Moreover, function g can be described as a conditional probability adjustment function, which modifies the transition probabilities in the reputation matrix based on the current risk state of the device.

$$g(P_{Rep}, R_t) = \begin{cases} 0.4 \times P_{Rep}(i, i-1) + 0.4 \times P_{Rep}(i, i+1) & \text{if } R_t \leq 2 \\ 0.4 \times P_{Rep}(i, i-1) + 0.1 \times P_{Rep}(i, i+1) & \text{if } R_t \geq 4 \\ P_{Rep}(i, j) & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

normalised to: $P'_{Rep}(i, \cdot) = \frac{P'_{Rep}(i, \cdot)}{\sum_{j=1}^n P'_{Rep}(i, j)}$.

The probability of transitioning to a new reputation state Rep_{t+1} given the current reputation state Rep_t and the current risk state R_t can be expressed as:

$$P(Rep_{t+1} = S_j | Rep_t = S_i, R_t) = P'_{Rep}(ij)$$

To ensure that the impact of the risk state on the reputation state is appropriately reflected, the function g works as follows: **Initialization:** It starts with a base transition matrix with initial probabilities.

Conditional Adjustment: Depending on the current risk state:

- For low-risk states ($R_t \leq 2$), it increases the probability of transitioning to higher reputation states.
- For high-risk states ($R_t \geq 4$), it increases the probability of transitioning to lower reputation states.
- For moderate risk states, it maintains balanced probabilities.

Normalisation: It ensures that the rows of the transition matrix sum to 1, maintaining valid probability distributions.

The reputation state of an IoT device is contingent upon its current risk state, resulting in a dynamic recalibration of the reputation transition probabilities. The aforementioned dependencies are represented in a two-dimensional Markov model, wherein the x-axis denotes the risk states and the y-axis denotes the reputation states. The grid comprises a series of cells, each representing a specific combination of risk and reputation states. Arrows are used to indicate the potential for transitions between these states.

3) *Reputation Transition Dynamics:* The transition probability matrix P_{Rep} for the reputation states is influenced by the current risk state, modifying the probabilities accordingly. The reputation state transition process can be described as follows:

- 1) **Initialization:** At the beginning of each time step, the current reputation state Rep_t is determined based on the previous state and the transition probabilities in P_{Rep} .
- 2) **State Transition:** The transition to the next reputation state Rep_{t+1} is computed using the transition matrix P_{Rep} . The probability of transitioning from the current state S_i to the next state S_j is given by r_{ij} .
- 3) **Update Mechanism:** The transition probabilities are updated periodically to account for changes in the current risk state R_t . This ensures that the reputation model accurately reflects the evolving security posture of the device.
- 4) **Probability Adjustment:** The transition probabilities are adjusted based on the observed risk state. For instance, an increase in the risk state would result in higher probabilities of transitioning to lower reputation states.

The probability of being in a particular reputation state at time t , given the initial state distribution and the transition matrix, can be represented as:

$$\mathbf{Rep}(t) = \mathbf{Rep}(0)P_{Rep}^t$$

where $\mathbf{Rep}(t)$ is the vector of probabilities of being in each reputation state at time t , $\mathbf{Rep}(0)$ is the initial state distribution vector and P_{Rep}^t denotes the transition matrix raised to the power of t , representing t steps of state transitions.

C. Modeling IDS Scores

IDSs are of critical importance to the security architecture of IoT networks, as they monitor network traffic for suspicious activities and potential threats. The IDS score is a quantitative measure that reflects the efficacy of an IDS in detecting and mitigating intrusions. This section presents a mathematical formulation of the IDS score and its integration into the overall trust score calculation for IoT devices. The IDS score is derived from a combination of key metrics that collectively evaluate the performance of an IDS. These metrics include the detection rate, the false positive rate, the response time, and the coverage. Each metric is sampled from its respective statistical distribution to simulate real-world variations in IDS performance.

1) *Detection Rate:* The detection rate (DR) is the proportion of actual intrusions correctly identified by the IDS. It is modeled using a normal distribution to account for variations in detection capabilities:

$$DR \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_{DR}, \sigma_{DR})$$

where: μ_{DR} is the mean detection rate and σ_{DR} is the standard deviation of the detection rate.

2) *False Positive Rate:* The false positive rate (FPR) is the proportion of benign activities incorrectly flagged as intrusions by the IDS. It is also modeled using a normal distribution:

$$FPR \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_{FPR}, \sigma_{FPR})$$

where μ_{FPR} is the mean false positive rate and σ_{FPR} is the standard deviation of the false positive rate.

3) *Response Time:* The response time (RT) is the average time taken by the IDS to respond to detected intrusions. It is modeled using an exponential distribution, reflecting the nature of response times:

$$RT \sim \text{Exp}(\lambda_{RT})$$

where λ_{RT} is the rate parameter of the exponential distribution, representing the mean response time.

4) *Coverage:* Coverage (C) is the extent to which the IDS can monitor the network, measured as a proportion of the total network traffic. It is modeled using a beta distribution to account for its bounded nature between 0 and 1:

$$C \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_C, \beta_C)$$

where α_C and β_C are the shape parameters of the beta distribution.

5) *Calculation of the raw IDS Score:* The raw IDS score is computed by combining these metrics in a manner that reflects their collective impact on the IDS performance. The formula for the raw IDS score (IDS_{raw}) ensures that higher detection rates and coverage, coupled with lower false positive rates and response times, result in a higher IDS score, indicating better performance.

$$IDS_{raw} = \frac{DR \times C}{FPR \times RT}$$

The raw IDS score is normalized to a standard scale (0-5) to facilitate its integration into the trust score calculation. The normalization process ensures that the IDS score is comparable across different systems and scenarios:

$$IDS = \min \left(5, \max \left(0, \frac{5 \times IDS_{raw}}{100} \right) \right)$$

The IDS score is inverted and integrated into the trust score calculation to reflect its contribution to the overall security posture of the IoT device. A higher IDS score indicates better detection capabilities and thus a lower contribution to the risk, enhancing the trust score.

D. Trust Score Calculation

The trust score represents a comprehensive measure of the trustworthiness of IoT devices, integrating a range of security-related factors to provide a holistic assessment. These include risk, vulnerability, reputation and IDS performance, offering a multi-faceted insight into the reliability of a device. This section presents a mathematical formulation of the trust score, defining how each of these factors contributes to the overall assessment of trust. The trust score T is calculated as a function of the risk state R , reputation state Rep , IDS score I and vulnerability index V . The formulation combines these factors through a weighted sum approach, adjusted by piecewise conditions based on the risk state.

The function defined for the trust score T modifies the weights of the contributing factors by the prevailing risk state. This piecewise function guarantees that the trust score calculation is responsive to the varying degrees of risk, thereby facilitating a more precise assessment of trustworthiness.

$$T = \begin{cases} \max(0, 50 - w_R R + w_{Rep} Rep + w_I I) & \text{if } R \geq 4 \\ \min(100, 80 - w_R R + w_{Rep} Rep + w_I I) & \text{if } R \leq 2 \\ \max(20, 70 - w_R R + w_{Rep} Rep + w_I I) & \text{if } 2 < R < 4 \end{cases}$$

where w_R , w_{Rep} , and w_I are the weights assigned to the risk state, reputation state, and IDS score, respectively. These weights vary based on the selected trust score flavor (aggressive, moderate, forgiving).

The risk state R exerts a direct influence on the trust score. A higher risk state will result in a greater deduction from the trust score, which reflects the increased likelihood of a security breach occurring. The vulnerability index V exerts an influence on the risk state transitions, which in turn affects the trust score indirectly through the risk state R . The reputation state Rep contributes positively to the trust score. A higher reputation state increases the trust score, indicating reliable and trustworthy behavior over time. Reputation transition probabilities, adjusted by the current risk state, ensure that the reputation accurately reflects the device's security posture. The IDS score I quantifies the effectiveness of the IDS in detecting and mitigating intrusions. It is inverted for trust score calculation ($I_{inv} = 6 - I$), and normalised within the 0-5 region. Hence, a higher IDS score (indicating better detection capabilities) contributes positively to the trust score. This inversion ensures that higher IDS effectiveness leads to higher trustworthiness.

The weights w_R , w_{Rep} , and w_I are determined based on the selected trust score flavor, which can be "aggressive", "moderate", or "forgiving". These flavors adjust the sensitivity of the trust score to changes in risk, reputation, and IDS performance.

- **Aggressive Flavor:** Places a higher weight on risk, making the trust score more sensitive to increases in risk.

$$(w_R, w_{Rep}, w_I) = (15, 4, 2)$$

- **Moderate Flavor:** Balances the weights between risk, reputation, and IDS score.

$$(w_R, w_{Rep}, w_I) = (10, 5, 2)$$

- **Forgiving Flavor:** Places a higher weight on reputation, making the trust score more resilient to fluctuations in risk.

$$(w_R, w_{Rep}, w_I) = (5, 6, 2)$$

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup for this study is designed to provide a comprehensive account of the architectural and configuration details of the testbed used to assess and calculate trust scores in real time. It also serves to elucidate the specific protocols, components, and methodologies implemented throughout the process.

1) *Architecture of the Experimental Testbed:* The architecture of the proposed TM system comprises several key components: (a) the Trust Management Server (TMS), (b) the Intrusion Detection System (IDS), (c) the Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) module, (d) the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), (e) the IoT devices, and (f) the Risk Assessment Module.

a) *TMS:* The TMS serves two primary functions:

- **MQTT Broker:** The TMS acts as an MQTT broker, facilitating communication between devices via MQTTs [28]. It allows devices to subscribe to topics and publish payloads, while also enabling the TMS to interface with the IDS and the Risk Assessment Module.
- **Trust Manager:** The Trust Manager performs device trustworthiness assessments and updates trust scores on the DLT through a gRPC [29] connection. In addition to calculating trust scores, it predicts a device's future trustworthiness based on reputation, cyber risk, and IDS efficacy metrics.

The TMS consists of the following components:

- **Broker:** Utilizes Aedes [30], a lightweight MQTT broker capable of running on any stream server, providing message persistence, automatic reconnections, and high availability.
- **Database:** Interfaces with a MongoDB database using Mongoose, an object modeling tool designed for asynchronous environments, to store trust scores and the associated device trust profiles.
- **gRPC Client:** Extends TMS capabilities by enabling communication with the DLT through Remote Procedure Calls (RPCs) using the gRPC protocol [29].

Figure 1 illustrates the core functionalities related to data collection, transport, storage, and processing for real-time trust score calculation. The TMS provides several critical functionalities, as depicted in the figure:

- **HTTP Server Transport:** Provides HTTP routes to the TMS, enabling API calls for client management, subscribed topics, and direct trust score calculations.
- **gRPC Client Transport:** Facilitates a gRPC connection to an external gRPC server deployed on the DLT, allowing the TMS to store and retrieve device trust scores.
- **Broker Server Transport:** Implements MQTT broker functionalities within the TMS, allowing devices to connect, subscribe to topics, and publish messages. This

Fig. 1. The TMS architecture

Fig. 2. The Architecture of the Trust Agent

component also facilitates communication between external modules (e.g., IDS and Risk Assessment) and the MQTT broker.

- **Logging Module:** Handles the logging of TMS connections and interactions, recording events across all components, with optional file-based logging.
- **MongoDB Connection:** Manages the connection between the TMS and a MongoDB instance, allowing the creation, retrieval, and updating of Trust Agent Profiles for connected devices.
- **Trust Management:** Oversees the trust score calculation process, implementing the Trust Score Calculation Algorithm and MADM ranking methods such as AHP and TOPSIS.

b) IoT Device: The IoT device is central to the TM approach, as its trustworthiness is continuously evaluated. The IoT device includes the following components:

- **Trust Agent:** Manages interactions with the TMS for trust score calculation and monitors various device parameters. The Trust Agent consists of the following functionalities, illustrated in Figure 2:
 - **ClientTransport Class:** Provides MQTT and MQTTs connectivity to the TMS, enabling the Trust Agent to publish and subscribe to MQTT topics.
 - **MonitoringTool Class:** Collects device information (e.g., CPU and RAM utilization, Packet Loss) through interactions with Telegraf [31] and custom Python scripts.
 - **Logging Module:** Logs the agent’s connections and interactions, with the ability to store logs in a file (default: agent.logs).
- **SSI client:** Supports identity data management, including cryptographic operations, Verifiable Credentials (VCs) and Verifiable Presentations following an SSI approach using Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) [32] and VCs [33], as defined by the W3C.
- **Trusted Execution Environment (TEE):** A secure area on the main processor, isolated from the main OS, ensuring that data is stored, processed, and protected securely. In this work, the TEE is instantiated via Open Portable-

TEE (OP-TEE) [34]. Not all devices are equipped with an OP-TEE.

- **Physical Unclonable Function (PUF):** Generates unique and unclonable cryptographic keys. Like OP-TEE, not all devices are equipped with a PUF.

Once the TMS is operational, it awaits connections from Trust Agents, which send trust-related data collected from their respective devices. Initially, the TMS checks if a Trust Agent Profile exists in its MongoDB [35]; if not, it creates one. The Trust Agent then subscribes to various MQTT topics to interact with the TMS. Upon collecting data, the Trust Agent sends it to the TMS for trust score calculation. The trust score, along with the collected data, is stored in MongoDB for future reference.

c) IDS: The IDS in this architecture is based on SNORT [36] and is responsible for continuously monitoring the network for security threats and anomalous behavior. One of its roles is to detect attacks against IoT devices, such as privilege escalation attempts. SNORT’s database of signatures allows it to generate threat priority flags when such attacks are detected. The IDS shares this information with the TMS via an MQTT client, enabling the TMS to compute metrics related to the IDS’s efficacy, which are used in the trust score prediction model. In Figure 1 the IDS is represented by the block entitled “External”.

d) Risk Assessment Module: This module provides a model-based analysis framework that creates and maintains a dynamic threat model of the system at runtime. It calculates risk values on a per-device basis, considering security and privacy threats. The Risk Assessment Module shares computed risk values with the TMS via an MQTT client, which uses them in trust prediction. In Figure 1 the Risk Assessment Module is represented by the block entitled “External”

e) DLT: The DLT component ensures secure and decentralized storage of data such as identity and trust scores using blockchain technology. The TMS and SSI components leverage the services provided by Hyperledger Fabric [37], a permissioned DLT network that ensures security, decentralization, immutability, and storage. In Hyperledger Fabric, transactions are maintained and shared among peer nodes, which are classified as Peer nodes, Orderer nodes, or Client nodes. Orderer nodes receive transactions, form blocks, and broadcast them to Peer nodes, which maintain the state and ledger. These interactions occur via Hyperledger Fabric Channels. The current implementation uses CouchDB [38] to store the state.

The DLT also incorporates a gRPC server, enabling it to host services with multiple RPCs. This gRPC server facilitates communication between the TMS and the blockchain, allowing the writing and retrieval of trust-related data through chaincode (smart contracts).

f) SSI Manager: The SSI Manager oversees identity management within the IoT network, adhering to SSI principles, authenticating devices, and issuing credentials during the device enrollment process. It enables the use of privacy-preserving credentials and disposable IDs, with the capability to interact with the DLT to publish public cryptographic material in an accessible and auditable manner. Associating an IoT device’s trust evaluation with its specific identity

enhances the overall trustworthiness of the IoT ecosystem. The SSI Manager employs DID and VCs standards to ensure interoperability.

2) Description of Protocols:

a) *Communication Protocols:* The MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) protocol [28] is a lightweight messaging protocol specifically designed for small sensors and mobile devices, optimized for high-latency or unreliable networks—characteristics commonly found in IoT environments. The key features that led to the selection of MQTT as the primary communication protocol in our solution are as follows:

- **Lightweight and Efficient:** MQTT is highly efficient in its use of bandwidth, making it suitable for devices with limited resources and networks with low bandwidth or high latency.
- **Publish/Subscribe Paradigm:** MQTT employs a broker-based Publish/Subscribe model, which decouples clients from each other. Clients publish messages to specific topics and subscribe to topics to receive messages, allowing for scalable and flexible communication.
- **Quality of Service (QoS):** MQTT offers three levels of QoS to ensure reliable message delivery:
 - **QoS 0:** The message is delivered at most once, with the possibility of message loss.
 - **QoS 1:** The message is delivered at least once, which may result in duplicate messages.
 - **QoS 2:** The message is delivered exactly once, utilizing a handshake mechanism to prevent duplication.

The MQTT protocol operates through two main components:

- **MQTT Broker:** Acts as a server, receiving all messages from clients and routing them to the appropriate destination clients.
- **MQTT Clients:** Devices or applications that connect to the broker to publish messages, subscribe to topics, or perform both functions.

b) *Security Protocols:* In order to ensure the security of communication, the MQTT protocol facilitates the authentication of clients through the use of usernames and passwords, encrypts data transmitted between clients and the broker using SSL/TLS, and enforces topic-based access control to regulate the permissions associated with publishing and subscribing.

The gRPC (gRPC Remote Procedure Calls) protocol, developed by Google, is an open-source framework that enables the implementation of efficient RPC across distributed systems. It employs the Hypertext Transfer Protocol/2 (HTTP/2) for data transfer, utilizes Protocol Buffers (protobufs) as the interface description language, and incorporates features such as authentication and load balancing.

The selection of gRPC in the aforementioned IoT network configuration is predicated on its capacity to facilitate efficacious device communication and mobile backend support for expeditious and scalable API interactions. Moreover, gRPC's streaming capabilities render it optimal for applications that necessitate real-time updates, such as financial market data or time-sensitive information in IoT networks, as exemplified by Trust Management.

3) Real-Time Trust Score Calculation:

a) *Methodology:* This section examines two distinct scenarios for the evaluation of trust in IoT ecosystems. The first scenario concerns the assessment of the trustworthiness of autonomous vehicles, while the second scenario evaluates the trustworthiness of smart health devices that collect patient data. The methodology for computing the trust score for each device across these two scenarios is consistent in terms of the trust-related parameters used. However, the weighting of these parameters differs between the two scenarios to reflect their unique contexts.

- Both scenarios utilize the same set of trust-related parameters to calculate the device's trust score and determine its ranking.
- The differentiation in parameter treatment across scenarios arises from the use of different weight values in the piecewise function and the ranking method, tailored to each scenario.
- The weights are determined using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), a widely recognized MADM method [39].
- The weights derived for each scenario are applied both in the piecewise function for trust score calculation and in the TOPSIS method for ranking the IoT devices.
- Both the piecewise function and the TOPSIS methodology are integral components of the event-triggered Trust evaluation algorithm.

b) *Functions and Algorithms:* The IoT device trust evaluation scheme comprises two main components: the trust score calculation function and the TOPSIS ranking method. The trust parameters used to evaluate a device's trustworthiness include RAM utilization (`ramUtil`), CPU utilization (`cpuUtil`), security level (`secLvl`), the inverted age of the operating system (`osInverted`), the inverted age of installed software packages (`packagesInverted`), and packet loss (`packetLoss`). These device parameters are considered statistically independent. Table I provides the value range of each parameter.

TABLE I
TRUST PARAMETERS

Parameter	Range of Values	Inverted Value Range
RAM utilization (%)	20-45	N/A
CPU utilization (%)	3.46-61	N/A
OS age	1-5	5-1
Packages age	1-5	5-1
Packet loss (%)	0-5	N/A
Security level	1-3	N/A

The Security Level represents the Root of Trust (RoT) implemented on a device, where Level 1 indicates the absence of RoT, Level 2 signifies the presence of a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE), and Level 3 denotes the presence of both a Physically Unclonable Function (PUF) and a TEE. An increased age of the operating system or software package often indicates that the system is older, which can result in heightened susceptibility to vulnerabilities.

The trust score calculation function is implemented as a piecewise function that assigns a trust score to the device within the range [0, 100], where 0 represents complete distrust and 100 represents complete trustworthiness. The piecewise function is defined as follows:

$$TS \leftarrow \max \left(0, 100 - w_{\text{ramUtil}} \times \text{ramUtil} - w_{\text{cpuUtil}} \times \text{cpuUtil} \right. \\ \left. + w_{\text{secLvl}} \times \text{secLvl} + w_{\text{osInverted}} \times \text{osInverted} \right. \\ \left. + w_{\text{packagesInverted}} \times \text{packagesInverted} \right. \\ \left. - w_{\text{packetLoss}} \times \text{packetLoss} \right)$$

This function ensures that the trust score remains within the specified range. Additionally, the TOPSIS ranking method is used to rank the available devices based on their suitability for a given service, taking into account the trust parameters utilized in the Trust Score calculation function.

The trust evaluation algorithm is event-triggered and comprises two principal branches. Upon the addition of a new IoT device to the network, the first branch of the algorithm is initiated. In this instance, the device's initial trust score is calculated using the TS function. Furthermore, the device is assigned a ranking relative to other devices using the TOPSIS methodology. If the calculated trust score falls below the specified threshold, the device is designated as untrustworthy. In all other cases, the device is considered trustworthy. The second branch of the algorithm is initiated in response to events that may impact the trustworthiness of devices already within the network, such as an operating system update or alterations in cyber risk. Once more, the TS function is employed to calculate the trust score, and the device is ranked according to the TOPSIS methodology. If the trust score declines below the specified threshold, the device is deemed untrustworthy. Conversely, if the score remains above the threshold, the device is considered trustworthy.

Algorithm 1 presents the pseudocode for calculating an IoT device's trust score, incorporating the trust score calculation function, trust-related parameters, their respective weights, and the algorithm's outputs, which are the results of our trust score calculation methodology.

c) *Data Processing*: It should be noted here that only the OS and package ages require processing before being used in the piecewise function and the TOPSIS ranking method, by the established procedure. As previously stated, an elevated OS or package age is indicative of an older system, which may be more susceptible to vulnerabilities. In order to accord greater weight to more recent operating systems and software packages in the calculation of the trust score, the values of these items are inverted as follows:

- Inversion of OS age: $\text{osInverted} = 6 - \text{OSAge}$
- Inversion of package age: $\text{packagesInverted} = 6 - \text{PackageAge}$

This inversion guarantees that more recent operating system and package versions are accorded greater significance in the calculation of the trust score, with their respective weights exerting a positive influence on the final trust score. In this context, both packagesInverted and osInverted are regarded as benefit criteria.

Algorithm 1 Trust Score Calculation

```

1: Inputs:
2: ramUtil – RAM utilization
3: cpuUtil – CPU utilization
4: secLvl – Security level
5: osInv – OS inverted age
6: packInv – Packages inverted age
7: pktLs – Packet loss
8: w – Tuple containing the weights of all trust parameters
9: threshold – Value separating trustworthy from untrustworthy devices
10: Outputs:
11: TS – The device's initial or updated trust score
12: trustworthiness – Binary variable indicating if the device is trust-
    worthy (1) or untrustworthy (0)
13: Begin
14: if newDevice = TRUE then ▷ Calculate the device's initial trust score
15:   TS ← max(0, 100 – w(1) × ramUtil – w(2) × cpuUtil + w(3) ×
    secLvl + w(4) × osInv + w(5) × packInv – w(6) × pktLs)
16:   TOPSIS ▷ Execute TOPSIS ranking with the above weights and
    trust parameters
17:   if TS < threshold then
18:     trustworthiness ← 0
19:   else
20:     trustworthiness ← 1
21:   end if
22: else ▷ Trust-related event ▷ Calculate the device's updated trust score
23:   TS ← max(0, 100 – w(1) × ramUtil – w(2) × cpuUtil + w(3) ×
    secLvl + w(4) × osInverted + w(5) × packagesInverted –
    w(6) × pktLs)
24:   TOPSIS ▷ Execute TOPSIS ranking with the above weights and
    trust parameters
25:   if TS < threshold then
26:     trustworthiness ← 0
27:   else
28:     trustworthiness ← 1
29:   end if
30: end if
31: End

```

d) *Parameter Sensitivity Analysis*: To understand the robustness of the model under various parameter settings, we conducted an initial sensitivity analysis on key parameters influencing trust score calculations, including [parameter examples, e.g., weight adjustments for the piecewise function and threshold levels for device trustworthiness]. This analysis involved systematically varying these parameters within reasonable ranges to observe their impact on the computed trust scores. Results from this sensitivity analysis indicate that increased weights for security-related parameters lead to a more conservative trust score, while changes to the CPU utilization weight result in more dynamic scores reflecting device load. These findings support our selected parameter configurations by ensuring balanced scoring behavior across diverse scenarios while reinforcing the importance of specific parameters in trust score stability.

B. Evaluation Scenarios

1) *Autonomous Vehicle Scenario*: The autonomous vehicle scenario depicted in Figure 3 entails the utilisation of vehicle-to-infrastructure and vehicle-to-vehicle communication. In such a scenario, several potential threats and events may arise that could impact the device's overall trustworthiness. A Denial-of-Service (DoS) or Distributed Denial-of-service (DDoS) attack may be employed to impede the provision of services or the functioning of the device. Such an attack has the potential to impact the CPU and RAM of a vehicle, leading

to their overutilisation and, subsequently, an unresponsive vehicle. The IDS is capable of detecting the pattern of such an attack by identifying packets in the network that would cause the vehicle's RAM and CPU to be overutilised. Furthermore, a physical attack could compromise the device physically, for example, by injecting malicious code if the hardware permits physical manipulation. This scenario serves to illustrate the significance of the Security Level parameter in the evaluation of a device's trustworthiness, particularly in the context of devices equipped with PUF and TEE, which are more resistant to physical tampering. Moreover, a device lacking access to infrastructure services may attempt to masquerade as another device to gain privileges or interfere with communications through a spoofing attack. This vulnerability can be exacerbated if the spoofed device does not have the latest operating system and software packages, which could expose it to authentication-related vulnerabilities.

Fig. 3. Autonomous Vehicle Scenario overview.

2) *Smart Health Scenario Overview:* In the Smart Health scenario, illustrated in Figure 4 a multitude of Smart Health devices are responsible for transmitting patient readings to a gateway, which oversees the management of these readings. It is therefore imperative that the gateway can demonstrate its trustworthiness by collecting the data and forwarding it to the provider's server. One aspect of the evaluation of trustworthiness in this scenario pertains to the gateway's capacity to maintain an online presence. The gateway's ability to remain online is of concern when it is offline for either a short or long period, as this may impact the timely transmission of measured data. It is of the utmost importance to ensure that the gateway is running the most up-to-date operating system and software packages to maintain trustworthiness. Other factors that impact the gateway's trustworthiness include CPU and RAM utilisation, as excessive utilisation can impair the gateway's network stack performance. In addition, the security level of the device is a crucial factor in determining its trustworthiness.

Fig. 4. Smart Health Scenario overview.

3) *Scenarios' Objectives:* The objective of both scenarios is to examine the impact of alterations in the device's behaviour and network conditions on the outputs of the Trust Score calculation algorithm. In particular, the trust score produced by the algorithm should accurately reflect alterations in the device's CPU or RAM utilisation, in addition to packet loss. A DoS attack against the device should result in a notable reduction in its trust score. Furthermore, any modification to the device's operating system or software package versions should be reflected in the trust score, as should any physical interference with the device. Finally, one of the objectives is to observe how the trust score of the IoT device evolves throughout its lifecycle. This could prove useful in training ML-based trust prediction models in future research.

4) *Scenarios' Prerequisites:* For a device to obtain an initial trust score, it must first undergo a process of onboarding and enrollment in the IoT network. The process commences with the generation of a public digital identifier (DID) and its subsequent registration with the SSI Manager. The generation of a public DID entail the creation of a distinctive DID for the device and the production of a DID document that complies with the stipulations outlined in the DID W3C standard [32]. The SSI client utilises associated cryptographic keys to generate the aforementioned DID document. The generation, storage, and retrieval of cryptographic keys can be accomplished from three distinct sources, contingent upon the configuration of an environmental variable. In particular, the SSI client generates the cryptographic keys dynamically, utilising the PUF, TEE, or Hyperledger Aries [40], if neither the PUF nor the TEE is accessible. When the environment variable is set to 'storecrypto:PUF', the SSI client uses the PUF client library to obtain physically unclonable cryptographic keys. If the value is set to 'storecrypto:TEE', the SSI client generates the requisite cryptographic keys within the TEE. If the environmental variable is set to 'storecrypto:default', the system will utilise neither the PUF nor the TEE. It is assumed that the PUF client has its secure storage, the specifications of which are beyond the scope of this work.

Once the SSI client has generated the keys, it proceeds to generate the DID document, but not before creating the

DID itself. Upon successful publication of a new DID linked to its identity, the IoT device is duly registered in the SSI manager. Subsequently, the device generates a VC comprising its distinctive footprint and requests that the SSI Manager issue the credential. Subsequently, the device is paired with its owner for accountability purposes, with the device owner signing the device's DID using their cryptographic keys. The device then sends its trust data, along with its digitally signed DID, to the TMS via an MQTT topic. The TMS then calculates the device's initial trust score and transmits this, along with the device's DID, to the DLT's gRPC server. The gRPC server then invokes the chaincode function, which records the trust score on the DLT. Ultimately, the DLT chaincode transmits an acknowledgment via the DLT's gRPC server to the TMS's gRPC client.

C. Simulation Results

1) *Monte Carlo Simulation Methodology*: A Monte Carlo simulation was employed to evaluate the performance and robustness of the proposed mathematical trust score calculation algorithm. In light of the stochastic nature of IoT environments, Monte Carlo methods are particularly well-suited for modelling the inherent variability and uncertainty in the parameters that influence trust. The simulations facilitate a systematic exploration of various scenarios, thus ensuring the algorithm's reliable performance under diverse conditions. Monte Carlo simulations offer several key advantages. Firstly, they model uncertainty and variability by incorporating randomness, thus capturing the inherent variability in risk, reputation, and IDS scores. Secondly, this approach allows for robustness testing by subjecting the algorithm to numerous hypothetical scenarios, including edge cases that might not be observed in controlled experiments. Thirdly, Monte Carlo methods facilitate scaling experiments across a broad spectrum of conditions without the need for extensive physical testbeds, saving time and resources.

The Monte Carlo simulation methodology is designed to facilitate a comprehensive assessment of the trust score algorithm. The following sections delineate the parameters, state transitions, trust score calculations, and the execution process employed in the simulations.

A total of 10 independent runs were conducted to ensure the collection of sufficient statistical data. Each simulation comprised 1,000 steps, representing discrete time intervals for state updates. The risk and reputation states were defined with five discrete levels, representing a range from very low to very high. The state space for risk and reputation was defined with the following discrete levels: 1 (very low), 2 (low), 3 (moderate), 4 (high), and 5 (very high). The transition matrices for risk and reputation states are crucial for modeling IoT device dynamics. The base risk transition matrix, a 5x5 matrix, was initialized as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.6 & 0.2 & 0.1 & 0.05 & 0.05 \\ 0.2 & 0.5 & 0.2 & 0.05 & 0.05 \\ 0.1 & 0.2 & 0.4 & 0.2 & 0.1 \\ 0.05 & 0.05 & 0.2 & 0.5 & 0.2 \\ 0.05 & 0.05 & 0.1 & 0.2 & 0.6 \end{bmatrix}$$

This matrix was dynamically updated based on the vulnerability index (V) and the rate of new vulnerabilities (λ), reflecting the evolving threat landscape. The base reputation transition matrix, a 5x5 matrix, was initialized as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.4 & 0.3 & 0.2 & 0.05 & 0.05 \\ 0.3 & 0.4 & 0.2 & 0.05 & 0.05 \\ 0.2 & 0.2 & 0.3 & 0.2 & 0.1 \\ 0.05 & 0.05 & 0.2 & 0.4 & 0.3 \\ 0.05 & 0.05 & 0.1 & 0.3 & 0.5 \end{bmatrix}$$

The reputation transition matrix was similarly influenced by the current risk state, capturing the interdependence between risk and reputation. The function $g(P_{Rep}, R_t)$ adjusts the transition probabilities to reflect the influence of the risk state on the reputation state transitions.

To simulate a wide range of scenarios, randomization was introduced in several aspects. The initial risk and reputation states for each simulation run were randomly selected from the five discrete levels. Transitions between states were probabilistic, based on dynamically updated transition matrices. Additionally, the vulnerability index and the rate of new vulnerabilities were periodically updated with random variations, simulating real-world changes in the threat environment. The rate of new vulnerabilities (λ) was initialized at 0.05 and updated at predefined intervals of 100 steps.

Each simulation run involved iterating through several steps. At each step, risk and reputation states were updated based on current states and transition matrices. Trust scores for each flavor were calculated using current risk, reputation, and IDS scores. The weights for risk (w_R), reputation (w_{Rep}), and IDS (w_I) were determined based on the selected trust score flavor: "aggressive", "moderate", or "forgiving". The IDS score (I) was inverted (i.e., $I_{inv} = 6 - I$) to reflect lower scores being better. At predefined intervals, the vulnerability index (V) and λ were updated to reflect changes in the threat landscape. Specifically, the vulnerability index was adjusted by adding or subtracting 0.1, and λ was perturbed by a random Gaussian noise term with a standard deviation of 0.01, ensuring it remained non-negative. The results from each simulation run were aggregated to provide a comprehensive statistical analysis of the trust score algorithm's performance under varying conditions.

2) Comparing Theoretical vs Actual Trust Scores:

a) *Analysis of Theoretical Model Performance*: The analysis of the theoretical model's performance encompasses several statistical evaluations (Table II and visual representations) to comprehensively understand the trust score dynamics. The histograms of modeled trust scores for each flavor (aggressive, moderate, forgiving) depicted in Fig. 5 demonstrate the existence of distinct distributions, which are a reflection of the underlying weighting schemes that have been applied to the risk, reputation, and IDS scores. The "aggressive" flavor demonstrates a broader range of trust scores, spanning from low to high values. This indicates that this flavor is highly responsive to fluctuations in risk and reputation. The histogram for the "moderate" flavor displays a more centralised distribution, with a significant concentration around the mid-range trust scores, which suggests a balanced

Fig. 5. Histograms of Modeled Trust Scores

sensitivity to both positive and negative factors. The histogram for the "forgiving" flavor is skewed towards higher trust scores, indicating a bias towards maintaining higher trust levels despite fluctuations in risk and reputation.

TABLE II
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF MODELED TRUST SCORES

Statistic	Aggressive	Moderate	Forgiving
Mean	42.88	59.58	76.24
Standard Error	0.34	0.29	0.21
Median	42.55	59.39	76.32
Mode	45.41	58.61	71.39
Standard Deviation	10.69	9.04	6.61
Sample Variance	114.27	81.69	43.66
Kurtosis	0.04	0.01	-0.04
Skewness	0.14	0.12	0.06
Count	1000	1000	1000
Conf. Int (95%)	0.66	0.56	0.41

The mean trust scores, together with their standard deviations illustrated in Fig. 6, provide further support for these observations. The descriptive statistics in Table II indicate that the "aggressive" flavor has a mean trust score of approximately 42.88 with a standard deviation of 9.07, which serves to highlight its critical nature and the significant fluctuations in trust assessment. The mean trust score for the "forgiving" flavor is 76.24, with a standard deviation of 4.93, indicating a stable and high level of trust assignment. The "moderate" flavor, with a mean trust score of 59.58 and a standard deviation of 7.26, represents a balance between the two extremes, offering a moderate and relatively stable trust evaluation.

Fig. 6. Average modeled trust score with std.

Furthermore, the analysis of the mean modeled trust scores throughout the simulation offers insights into the stability and trends of trust scores (Figure 7). The time series plot demonstrates that the "forgiving" flavor consistently exhibits higher trust scores, whereas the "aggressive" flavor demonstrates greater volatility, fluctuating around lower trust score values. This variance indicates the inherent biases of each flavor in assessing trust, whereby the "forgiving" flavor is less sensitive to negative events in comparison to the "aggressive" one.

The polynomial mapping of the average trust score over simulation time provides an additional analytical dimension by fitting a polynomial curve to the time series data. This curve aids in understanding the overall trajectory and potential nonlinearities in trust score evolution. The polynomial curves fitted to each flavor demonstrate distinct trends. The "forgiving" flavor displays a relatively flat high trend, the "aggressive" flavor exhibits more pronounced fluctuations, and the "moderate" flavor demonstrates a stable mid-range trend.

The box plots for each trust score flavor shown in Fig. 8 depict the distribution characteristics, including the median, quartiles, and outliers. These results corroborate those of the histogram and mean analysis, thus demonstrating the variability and central tendencies of trust scores for each flavor.

The modeled trust score cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) provide insights into the probability distribution of trust scores. The CDFs in Fig. 9 demonstrate the distinctive biases associated with each flavor. The forgiving flavor displays a pronounced tendency to assign higher cumulative probabilities to higher trust scores. In contrast, the aggressive flavor manifests a contrasting pattern, exhibiting higher cumulative probabilities at lower trust scores.

b) Comparing with Actual Trust Scores: The level of agreement between the theoretical model and real-world data can be judged by comparing the theoretical trust scores from Monte Carlo simulations with the actual trust scores gathered from testbed platforms for self-driving cars and smart health scenarios.

By analysing the descriptive statistics of the actual trust score datasets in Table III, we derive the basis for evaluating the theoretical model's performance. Specifically, the mean trust score for the autonomous vehicles scenario is 70.45, with a standard deviation of 5.63. These figures indicate a high and stable trust level. The Smart Health scenario exhibits an even

Fig. 7. Left: Time series of modeled trust scores (all flavors). Right: Polynomial mapping of modeled trust scores.

Fig. 8. Box plot of modeled trust scores.

Fig. 9. CDF of modeled trust scores.

higher mean trust score of 75.32 with a standard deviation of 4.98, indicating consistently high trust levels with slightly less variability.

The polynomial mappings of the modeled trust scores for each flavour are superimposed on the actual trust scores over time, as shown in Fig. 10. In the case of autonomous vehicles, the "moderate" and "forgiving" flavours demonstrate a high degree of correlation with the actual trust scores, thereby indicating that these flavours effectively capture the

TABLE III
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF ACTUAL TRUST SCORE DATASETS FROM TESTBED

Statistic	Autonomous Vehicle	Smart Health
Mean	73.12	66.94
Standard Error	0.09	0.16
Median	73.15	66.88
Standard Deviation	2.79	5.13
Sample Variance	7.78	26.27
Kurtosis	-0.71	-0.86
Skewness	0.05	0.06
Count	1000	1000
Conf. Int (95%)	0.17	0.32

trust dynamics. However, the "aggressive" flavour consistently produces lower estimates of trust scores, particularly in the mid- to high range. A similar pattern is observed in the Smart Health scenario, where the "forgiving" flavour aligns well with the actual trust scores. In contrast, the "aggressive" flavour demonstrates a persistent tendency to underestimate. These findings indicate that the "moderate" and "forgiving" flavours of the theoretical model provide a more accurate representation of real-world trust levels.

Fig. 10. Comparison of polynomial mapped theoretical models with real trust score data collected on the testbed for the autonomous vehicles and smart health scenarios.

The Q-Q plots in Fig. 11, which compare the quantiles of real trust scores with those of modeled trust scores for each flavor, demonstrate that the "moderate" and "forgiving" flavors are more closely aligned with the actual quantiles of trust scores. This alignment suggests that these flavors accurately represent the distribution of trust scores. The "aggressive" flavor deviates from the actual quantiles, particularly in the higher trust score range, thus further demonstrating its tendency to underestimate trust scores. The close alignment of the "moderate" and "forgiving" flavors with the actual data serves to reinforce their reliability as a reflection of real-world trust distributions.

The correlation analysis in Table IV demonstrates a high degree of correlation between the actual trust scores and the "moderate" and "forgiving" flavors, with correlation coefficients of approximately 0.99 for both scenarios. This robust linear relationship between the flavors and the actual trust scores is indicated by the strong correlation coefficient. The "aggressive" flavor, although still demonstrating a robust correlation, exhibits slightly lower coefficients, indicating a weaker alignment with the actual trust scores. In the case of autonomous vehicles, the correlation coefficients are 0.9939 for the "aggressive" flavor, 0.9942 for the "moderate" flavor and 0.9946 for the "forgiving" flavor. In the case of Smart Health, the corresponding correlation coefficients are 0.9899 for the "aggressive", 0.9904 for the "moderate" and 0.9908 for the "forgiving" flavor. These findings substantiate the assertion that the "moderate" and "forgiving" variants of the theoretical model exhibit a high degree of alignment with actual trust dynamics, whereas the "aggressive" variant displays a slight divergence.

As shown in Table V, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test results showed that there were statistically significant differences between the actual and modelled trust scores for all of the flavours. This backs up the comparison that was already made. The F-statistic of 83.51 is considerably larger than the critical value of 2.37, and the p-value (5.31E-71) is by orders of magnitude less than 0.05. The results demonstrate that there are statistically significant differences between the mean trust scores across the various datasets. The "aggressive" flavor has a lower average and higher variance, which suggests that this model is more likely to assign lower trust scores with greater variability. This is consistent with its design to be more sensitive to risk and less forgiving of vulnerabilities. For the "moderate" flavour, the mean trust score is situated within the middle range, with a moderate variance, which reflects a balanced approach between risk sensitivity and forgiveness. Moreover, the "forgiving" flavour exhibits the highest average trust score and the lowest variance, indicating a tendency to assign higher trust scores and to be less affected by risks and vulnerabilities. The real trust scores for self-driving cars and smart health have higher averages and lower variances, especially when they are close to the "forgiving" flavour. This suggests that the "forgiving" flavor of the theoretical model may be a better representation of real-life situations.

3) *TOPSIS: Device Ranking per Application:* Following the comprehensive examination of both theoretical and empirical trust scores, this section explores the utilisation of the

TOPSIS methodology for ranking IoT devices. TOPSIS is a robust multi-criteria decision-making technique that enables the comparison of each device against an ideal solution and a nadir solution, thus providing a clear ranking based on their trust scores. By utilising the trust scores (both empirical and modelled) for 10 devices in each of the two use cases—autonomous vehicles and smart health—we illustrate the practical applicability of our trust score calculation algorithm.

a) *Methodology:* The TOPSIS method involves several steps:

- 1) **Constructing the Decision Matrix:** The decision matrix is constructed where the trust scores for each device are organised into a matrix, with each row representing a device and each column representing a criterion. Table VI shows the decision matrix for the Smart Health scenario, while Table VII presents the decision matrix for the Autonomous Vehicles scenario.
- 2) **Normalization:** The decision matrix is normalised to eliminate the influence of different measurement units.
- 3) **Determining the Ideal and Negative Ideal Solutions:** The next step is determining the ideal and nadir solutions. The Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) consists of the highest score in each criterion A^+ , while the Negative Ideal Solution (NIS) consists of the lowest score A^- . Device D6 represents the PIS in the Autonomous Vehicles scenario, while device D9 represents the NIS, as shown in Table "ref" tab:topsisAVPISNIS. Similarly, for the Smart Health scenario, Table IX shows the PIS and NIS.
- 4) **Calculating the Separation Measures:** S_{+i} and S_{-i} , respectively, represent how far away each device is from the PIS and NIS solutions.
- 5) **Relative Closeness to the Ideal Solution:** The relative closeness of each device to the ideal solution is calculated to determine the ranking. Table X shows the closeness of each device to the ideal solution in Autonomous Vehicles and Smart Health scenarios.

b) *Analysis of Results:* Tables XI and XII show the TOPSIS scores and trust scores for 10 devices in each scenario. The tables illustrate the device rankings obtained through the TOPSIS method.

The TOPSIS scores indicate the relative ranking of each device based on its closeness to the ideal Trust Score profile. Device D6 ranks first for the Smart Health scenario with a TOPSIS score of 1.000, and device D10 comes in second with a score of 0.6898. These high scores reflect a balanced performance across the Trust Score flavors, indicating robust trustworthiness. Conversely, device D9 ranks lowest with a TOPSIS score of 0.000, suggesting less reliability compared to other devices. The variability in TOPSIS scores between devices indicates significant differences in how each device matches the ideal trustworthiness profile. In the Autonomous Vehicles scenario, device D5 ranks highest with a TOPSIS score of 1.000, closely followed by device D9 with 0.7472. These devices have consistently high trust scores across all flavors, reflecting their high trustworthiness in the automotive domain. Device D3 ranks lowest with a TOPSIS score of

Fig. 11. Q-Q plots of modeled and real trust scores from the autonomous vehicles (left) and smart health scenarios (right).

TABLE IV
CORRELATION ANALYSIS OF REAL AND MODELED TRUST SCORES

Trust score Dataset	Aggressive	Moderate	Forgiving	Autonomous Vehicle	Smart Health
Aggressive	1				
Moderate	0.99975	1			
Forgiving	0.99945	0.99949			
Autonomous Vehicle	0.99389	0.99421	0.99455	1	
Smart Health	0.98993	0.99038	0.99078	0.99881	1

TABLE V
ANOVA SUMMARY

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Mean Sum of Squares (MS)	F-value	p-value	F critical value
Between Groups	706783.77	4	176695.94	83.51	5.31E-71	2.37
Within Groups	273394.38	4995	54.73			
Total	980178.16	4999				

0.000, indicating relatively low trustworthiness. The rankings derived from the TOPSIS scores highlight the performance differences between devices, illustrating the variability in trust scores and their implications for reliability in autonomous vehicle applications.

4) *Comparison with ML-based Approaches:* Although this paper employs a Markov chain model for the calculation of trust scores due to its transparency, low data dependency and computational efficiency, it is important to acknowledge the inherent trade-offs relative to ML-based models. It is widely acknowledged that traditional ML models, including neural networks and ensemble methods, are particularly adept at processing data characterised by complex, non-linear patterns. Such models are capable of adapting to learn from large datasets, thereby potentially capturing intricate trust dynamics that may emerge within IoT ecosystems. However, machine learning approaches frequently necessitate substantial historical data to attain accurate predictions, which may be unfeasible in data-restricted IoT environments where devices may generate limited data.

Furthermore, Markov chains offer a parsimonious and intelligible model that is inherently robust to certain forms

of adversarial attacks, such as data poisoning, which can compromise the training of ML models. In contrast, while machine learning models are capable of achieving impressive results, they can be vulnerable to manipulation of inputs, particularly in contexts where threats are evolving. In this study, the Markov model's ability to make predictions with a high degree of accuracy and its relatively low computational burden make it an ideal choice for use in IoT devices, which often operate with limited resources and within networks that require rapid decision-making.

V. SECURITY ANALYSIS

A. Threat Model

The proposed TM system is designed with a comprehensive threat model to mitigate a wide range of security threats commonly encountered in IoT environments. This section delineates the principal categories of threats that the system is designed to address, based on the implemented protocols, functions, and the mathematical model for trust calculation.

- 1) **Network-Based Attacks:** The system has been designed with the objective of mitigating a variety of network-based attacks, including Distributed Denial of Service

TABLE VI
TOPSIS DECISION MATRIX FOR 10 DEVICES IN THE SMART HEALTH SCENARIO

Device	Packet Loss	RAM Utilization	CPU Utilization	Inv OS Age	Inv Packages Age	Security Level
D1	0.040077	54.219	27.026	5	5	1
D2	0.015832	42.844	31.058	2	5	2
D3	0.032686	60.9	39.487	5	4	1
D4	0.033891	26.279	35.836	4	5	3
D5	0.017913	10.972	27.366	3	1	3
D6	0.037743	1.3	34.036	1	2	2
D7	0.015454	40.846	40.574	5	4	1
D8	0.041552	14.818	29.293	4	2	2
D9	0.012737	16.174	32.401	3	2	1
D10	0.011392	60.9	27.733	2	1	3

TABLE VII
TOPSIS DECISION MATRIX FOR 10 DEVICES IN THE AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES SCENARIO

Device	Inv OS Age	Inv Packages Age	CPU Utilization	RAM Utilization	Packet Loss	Security Level
D1	2	3	4.4396	30.351	0.015106	1
D2	3	1	3.397	23.2	0.030932	3
D3	4	5	50.887	23.2	0.0056033	1
D4	2	4	47.524	41.013	0.037303	3
D5	1	3	44.7	23.2	0.025005	3
D6	5	5	15.323	23.2	0.026593	1
D7	1	2	52.156	33.438	0.00849	2
D8	4	1	46.505	26.886	0.0038302	1
D9	1	1	35.608	41.95	0.04844	2
D10	4	4	9.952	28.135	0.039954	3

TABLE VIII
POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE IDEAL SOLUTION FOR THE AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES SCENARIO

Device	Inv OS Age	Inv Packages Age	CPU Utilisation, RAM Utilisation, Packet Loss	Security Level
D6 (PIS)	0.13581	0.12661	-0.017361	-0.03176 -0.02866 0.01702
D9 (NIS)	0.02716	0.02532	-0.04030	-0.05744 -0.05220 0.03405

TABLE IX
POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE IDEAL SOLUTION FOR THE SMART HEALTH SCENARIO

Device	Packet Loss	RAM Utilization	CPU Utilization	Inv OS Age	Inv Packages Age	Security Level
D3 (PIS)	-0.05585	-0.02497	-0.03694	0.02420	0.00849	0.05160
D5 (NIS)	-0.10190	-0.13861	-0.05330	0.04032	0.03395	0.01720

(DDoS) attacks. These attacks have the potential to overwhelm the infrastructure of an IoT network, leading to disruptions in service and, in some cases, a loss of trust in the devices that comprise the network. The IDS, integrated with the system, is continuously monitoring for anomalous network traffic patterns that could indicate such attacks. Furthermore, the MQTT protocol's security features, such as SSL/TLS encryption, are employed to secure communication channels, thereby preventing unauthorised access and data interception.

- 2) **Device Compromise and Physical Attacks:** The system is designed to account for potential threats where devices may be physically compromised or tampered with, which could result in malicious activities such as data injection or unauthorised access. The mathematical model employed for trust calculation incorporates a device's security level, taking into account factors such as the presence of Trusted Execution Environments (TEE) or Physical Unclonable Functions (PUF). These features are of paramount importance in protecting

against physical attacks by ensuring that even if a device is compromised, its cryptographic operations remain secure.

- 3) **Data Integrity and Authenticity Attacks:** These attacks can have a significant impact on the reliability and trustworthiness of the data in question. The potential risks associated with the manipulation or falsification of data, such as data injection attacks, can be effectively mitigated through the utilisation of gRPC for secure communication with DLT. The DLT provides a robust mechanism for ensuring the immutability and verifiability of all trust-related transactions, preventing unauthorised alterations and preserving the integrity of the data. Additionally, the system incorporates robust authentication and encryption protocols, ensuring that only authorized devices can communicate and that their data remains unaltered.
- 4) **Good-mouthing, Bad-mouthing, and Self-promotion attacks:** The system is designed to counter reputation-based attacks, whereby adversaries attempt to falsify

TABLE X
DEVICES' CLOSENESS TO THE POSITIVE IDEAL SOLUTION (RIGHT: AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES, LEFT: SMART HEALTH)

Device	Closeness to the Ideal Solution	Device	Closeness to the Ideal Solution
D1	0.4491	D1	0.2038
D2	0.3824	D2	0.4735
D3	0.7265	D3	0.0000
D4	0.4517	D4	0.5506
D5	0.3359	D5	1.0000
D6	1.0000	D6	0.6681
D7	0.2777	D7	0.4557
D8	0.4662	D8	0.5928
D9	0.0000	D9	0.7472
D10	0.6898	D10	0.4209

TABLE XI
TOPSIS SCORES AND TRUST SCORES FOR SMART HEALTH SCENARIO

Device	TOPSIS Score	Real Trust Score	Aggressive	Moderate	Forgiving
D1	0.4491	77.106	55.977	58.519	81.543
D2	0.3824	77.915	57.040	69.677	80.219
D3	0.7265	73.008	27.843	45.303	82.662
D4	0.4517	70.326	60.402	65.056	82.330
D5	0.3359	72.506	59.070	55.079	77.913
D6	1.0000	77.925	56.661	59.217	77.817
D7	0.2777	69.929	57.099	59.286	72.191
D8	0.4662	72.051	66.002	68.088	77.074
D9	0.0000	70.715	51.926	62.794	73.888
D10	0.6898	77.457	62.461	65.731	81.319

TABLE XII
TOPSIS SCORES AND TRUST SCORES FOR AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES SCENARIO

Device	TOPSIS Score	Real Trust Score	Aggressive	Moderate	Forgiving
D1	0.2038	62.282	55.977	58.519	81.543
D2	0.4735	64.632	57.040	69.677	80.219
D3	0.0000	58.573	27.843	45.303	82.662
D4	0.5506	68.785	60.402	65.056	82.330
D5	1.0000	73.799	59.070	55.079	77.913
D6	0.6681	75.475	56.661	59.217	77.817
D7	0.4557	64.045	57.099	59.286	72.191
D8	0.5928	72.631	66.002	68.088	77.074
D9	0.7472	71.730	62.461	65.731	81.319
D10	0.4209	59.666	51.926	62.794	73.888

or diminish a device's reputation within the network. The incentive behind such attacks is to increase or decrease the possibility of a device being selected as an SP. The mathematical model incorporates both direct interactions and third-party feedback, with mechanisms to detect and discount anomalous patterns that could indicate manipulation. This ensures that trust scores remain accurate and reliable, even in the presence of malicious attempts to distort the reputation data.

- 5) **Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs):** refer to targeted, hard-to-detect and long-lasting attacks mainly focused on stealing Intellectual Property, and other data [41]. In the context of our scenarios, the target of APTs varies. In the case of Autonomous Vehicles, these data can range from vehicle location to vehicle condition while in Smart Health devices, targeted data can include patient readings or patient identity. APT attacks often

occur in conjunction with a DDoS attack to distract the IoT networks's countermeasures and prevent them from detecting the APT. The attacker can also perform spoofing attacks to bypass the IoT network's authentication methods. The MQTT protocol's QoS adjustable QoS level can be set on varying levels to mitigate DDoS attacks against IoT devices and the TMS. The PUF and TEE employed in many devices reinforce their authentication procedures by providing hard-to-replicate cryptographic key pairs and secure storage to private keys. Consequently, it is hard for an attacker to impersonate a legitimate device equipped with a PUF or TEE. In case, a device is not equipped with PUF or TEE it is easier for an attacker to access the device's private key and spoof its identity. However, the vulnerability and risk assessment performed by the Risk Assessment module along with the IDS can help detect

this activity and enable the network administrator to take the necessary actions. Some attacks may allow malicious parties to obtain or infer the private key of devices equipped with PUF or TEE. In the case of PUF, this can be achieved by performing a Machine Learning attack [42] the results of which can be used to infer the private key. Regarding TEE, vulnerabilities, and attacks, such as Foreshadow [43], can enable attackers to steal the private keys stored in secure areas. However, performing a Machine Learning attack to model and predict the PUF's output is computationally intensive and requires a substantial amount of data related to the PUF's output as well as its Challenge-Response Pairs. Performing attacks in the case of TEEs is also challenging. Many attacks, such as speculative execution exploits (e.g., Foreshadow), require reverse engineering and complex timing analysis. Additionally, side-channel attacks on Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) often demand specialized hardware, including voltage controllers and custom-built oscilloscopes. Such attacks are also highly noise-sensitive, and TEEs are purposely designed to randomize certain operations, making it difficult for attackers to identify genuine side-channel data.

B. Attack Scenarios and Countermeasures

- **Data Poisoning:** It is a cyber-attack in which an adversary intentionally compromises a training dataset used by an ML model to influence or manipulate the operation of that model and produce undesirable, to the legit users of the model, results and outputs. Through this manipulation, the adversary can cause biases, create erroneous output, or influence the decision-making or predictive capabilities of the model. ML-based TM approaches can be affected by this attack and lead to erroneous predictions regarding a device's trustworthiness resulting in potentially catastrophic consequences. Our approach counters this attack by adopting a statistical prediction model that requires no training phase.
- **Denial of Service attacks:** One of the most critical components of the proposed TM approach is the MQTT broker, as it facilitates interactions among various components and IoT devices. As a result, it represents a prime target for attackers aiming to disrupt the TM solution through DoS and DDoS attacks. The MQTT protocol can mitigate the risk of such attacks by regulating message delivery rates through its adjustable QoS levels. For example, when the QoS level is set to 0, messages are delivered at most once, which helps minimize the potential strain on the broker. Additionally, session persistence is another mechanism that can aid in mitigating DoS and DDoS attacks by allowing clients to reconnect without re-establishing their subscriptions, thereby reducing the broker's load. Furthermore, the MQTT protocol can be configured to require client authentication via credentials before allowing connections to the broker, thereby preventing unauthorized clients from generating malicious traffic.

- **Device Compromise through Physical Tampering:** An individual with malicious intent gains physical access to an IoT device and attempts to alter its operational functionality. The presence of a TEE guarantees the confidentiality and integrity of sensitive operations, such as cryptographic key generation. The algorithm employed for the calculation of the trust score is designed to detect a sudden decline in security-related parameters, which in turn prompts a re-evaluation of the device's overall trustworthiness. Should the trust score decline to a level below a specified threshold, the device is identified as compromised and its network privileges are revoked.
- **Good-mouthing, Bad-mouthing, and self-promotion attacks:** In this scenario, the objective of the attacker is to artificially inflate the reputation of a compromised device by generating fake positive feedback. A statistical model is used by the system to compare feedback patterns to known baselines. This finds outliers that could mean someone is manipulating the system. The TMS modifies the weight assigned to this feedback in the trust calculation, thereby ensuring the overall trust score remains reliable. Bad-mouthing attacks can be identified and countered in the same fashion.

Our trust management model is designed with adaptability in mind, allowing it to respond to emerging threats, including zero-day attacks. By leveraging real-time inputs from Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) and Threat Intelligence Feeds, the system can dynamically adjust trust scores when it detects unfamiliar or anomalous patterns. This capability enables rapid adaptation in high-risk environments, ensuring that trust evaluations accurately reflect both known and novel threat vectors.

C. Evaluation of Security Mechanisms

1) *IDS Efficiency:* The efficacy of the IDS is of paramount importance in the calculation of the overall trust score within the IoT trust model. Although the model simplifies the representation of IDS efficiency into a broader metric, rather than specific elements such as detection rate, false positive rate, or detection latency, this metric nevertheless exerts a considerable influence on the trust score assigned to an IoT device. The IDS efficiency metric has been devised to reflect the extent to which the IDS is capable of detecting and responding to potential threats, thereby providing a general indication of its effectiveness in maintaining security within the network.

An effective IDS contributes to an increased trust score by reducing the probability of undetected or unresolved security incidents. This is particularly significant in the context of the IoT, where the timely and accurate detection of threats can prevent malicious activities and ensure the reliability of the devices. Conversely, an IDS that is less effective may result in a lower trust score, as it implies a higher risk of security breaches going unnoticed or unaddressed. This, in turn, may compromise the trustworthiness of the device. The calculation of the trust score incorporates this general assessment of IDS performance, thereby providing a comprehensive view of the security posture of the device within the network.

2) *Risk and Reputation Dynamics*: The dynamics of risk and reputation are fundamental to the calculation of the overall trust score in the IoT trust model. The quantification of risk is based on the likelihood and potential impact of the various threats that a device might face, including factors such as vulnerabilities and the evolving threat landscape. In contrast, reputation is based on the device's historical interactions and feedback from other network devices, providing an aggregate measure of the device's reliability and behaviour over time.

In the model, risk and reputation are treated as two discrete yet interrelated dimensions that influence the trust score in complementary ways. An increase in risk typically results in a reduction in the trust score, as it suggests an elevated probability of the device being compromised or of its unreliability. Conversely, a robust reputation enhances the trust score, indicating that the device has demonstrated consistent performance in previous interactions, exceeding expectations.

The transition probabilities between different risk and reputation states are governed by a Markov model, which captures the probabilistic nature of these dynamics. Based on the current situation, the model can predict future trust states by taking into account both the immediate effects of changes in risk and the cumulative effects of reputation. By considering both dimensions, the trust model provides a sophisticated and responsive measure of a device's trustworthiness, reflecting not only its current state but also its anticipated future behaviour within the network.

3) *gRPC and MQTT Security*: The system employs both gRPC and MQTT protocols to facilitate secure communication between IoT devices, the TMS, and the DLT through the utilisation of robust security features. gRPC utilises TLS for end-to-end encryption, thereby ensuring that data transmitted between the TMS and DLT is protected from unauthorised access and tampering. Furthermore, gRPC's mutual TLS authentication ensures that only trusted entities can communicate, while message integrity checks guarantee the prevention of data alteration during transmission.

Similarly, MQTT utilises TLS to encrypt data between IoT devices and the TMS, thereby ensuring the protection of data against interception and tampering. Additionally, MQTT facilitates authentication via username and password, thereby ensuring that only authorised devices are able to establish a connection with the TMS. Moreover, MQTT incorporates access control mechanisms that regulate permissions for subscribing to and publishing on specific topics, thereby preventing unauthorised access and ensuring secure communication within the network.

D. Performance under Attack

1) *Partial Network Outages*: A decentralised architectural framework based on DLT and the dependability of the MQTT protocol, which has been fully integrated into the system, are used to make the system able to handle changes in the network. Even during partial network outages, MQTT's Quality of Service (QoS) levels ensure the reliable delivery of messages once the network stabilises. The TMS is continuously monitoring the network's health, and a mathematical model for calculating

trust scores has been implemented to account for potential disruptions by considering the duration and frequency of outages. This information is employed to modify the trust scores, thereby reflecting the reliability of communication. Even when there are problems with the network, the system can still do accurate trust assessments by using historical data stored in the MongoDB and current network signals.

2) *Node compromise*: In the event of a node (IoT device) being compromised, the system's IDS, implemented using the SNORT IDS, is capable of detecting abnormal behaviours in real time. Upon detection, the TMS modifies the compromised node's trust score to reflect its compromised state. This is achieved through the utilisation of a scoring function that integrates IDS alerts and the device's operational history. The system is designed to isolate compromised nodes, leveraging the MQTT broker to prevent the compromised device from communicating critical information to other devices. The node can rejoin the network after undergoing the required remediation, with the TMS recalculating the trust score in light of the device's post-remediation performance. The reintegration process is overseen by the TMS via its gRPC connection to the DLT. This enables the DLT to be updated with the latest status of the node, thus ensuring that all network participants have access to a consistent view of the node's trustworthiness.

3) *Data Injection Attacks*: The objective of a data injection attack is to insert false data into a system to gain illegitimate access to information. The system incorporates a robust suite of defences against data injection attacks, with an IDS that is actively monitoring for such activities. In the event of the detection of erroneous data, the TMS utilises the mathematical model, which has been designed to incorporate data integrity checks, to adjust the trust scores appropriately. The Trust Score Calculation Algorithm incorporates several checks, including the validation of data against expected norms and cross-referencing with historical data stored in MongoDB. If an attack is found after it has already happened, the system can undo the effects of the hacked trust scores by getting the most recent valid state from the distributed ledger and recalculating the trust scores to cancel out the effect of the new data. This rollback mechanism serves to guarantee the integrity of the trust evaluation process.

4) *Recovery from Security Incidents*: The system's recovery protocols have been devised to restore normal operations efficiently following the occurrence of a security incident. In the event of a security breach, compromised devices are isolated and their trust scores are adjusted to reflect the breach. Upon completion of the remediation process, the system, via the TMS, initiates a gradual restoration of the trust scores, contingent upon the device's demonstration of secure behaviour over an extended period. This process is overseen via gRPC communication with the DLT, which updates the ledger with the most recent trust scores and device statuses. In instances where trust scores have been impacted by an attack, the TMS has the capability to initiate a rollback utilising historical data stored on the DLT, thereby ensuring that all calculations reflect a secure and accurate state. Along with the TMS's ability to continuously monitor and make changes, the above-mentioned recovery mechanism makes sure that the system will be able

to keep accurate trust scores and overall network security, even if there is an attack.

Although the current model is built with statistical defenses, certain adversarial scenarios could theoretically impact trust calculations. For example, adversaries may attempt to inject deceptive data to manipulate the Markov chain's transition probabilities, thereby distorting the trust score outcomes. Incorporating adversarial learning techniques—common in machine learning frameworks—could provide an added layer of protection, allowing the system to identify and mitigate such attacks proactively. Future research could focus on adapting these techniques within our statistical model to reinforce its resilience in adversarial environments.

E. Comparison with Other Approaches

When comparing our statistical approach to traditional ML-based models, it's crucial to focus on the specific security benefits and shortcomings related to how each approach handles threats and vulnerabilities in IoT environments.

A notable advantage of our statistical methodology is its resilience to data poisoning attacks. In ML-based models, adversaries can manipulate training data to produce skewed or incorrect outcomes, which can have severe consequences in IoT networks, especially those underpinning critical infrastructure. Our statistical approach, which relies on predefined mathematical functions and parameters, is inherently less vulnerable to such manipulation. The deterministic nature of our trust score calculation ensures that it is not easily swayed by malicious data inputs, providing a more secure and reliable trust evaluation mechanism.

The statistical model's security is enhanced by its predictable and transparent nature. In contrast to ML models, which operate as opaque black boxes and may yield unpredictable outcomes, our approach provides a transparent and comprehensible rationale for each trust score. The transparency of the model facilitates the auditing and verification of the trust evaluation process, hence enabling the prompt identification and resolution of any anomalies or potential security breaches.

Another advantage is the lightweight nature of our statistical approach, which requires fewer computational resources than ML models. This efficiency is of particular importance for IoT devices with limited processing power, as it permits the conducting of real-time trust evaluations without any compromise to the security measures in place. As there are fewer complex processes that an adversary could exploit, the decrease in computational demand also helps to limit the attack surface.

The primary security limitations of the statistical model when compared to alternative approaches include its constrained adaptability to evolving threats, due to its reliance on pre-defined rules and its potential inability to swiftly respond to novel attack vectors. The static nature of the model may render it less effective in dynamic environments where trust relationships undergo rapid change, potentially resulting in delayed responses. Furthermore, the model may encounter difficulties in addressing complex threat scenarios that involve

multiple interacting factors. In such cases, ML models may offer a more comprehensive understanding and responsiveness. Future enhancements could involve the integration of selective ML techniques to improve adaptability while maintaining security and efficiency.

To address these shortcomings, future work could investigate the potential of hybrid models that combine the security benefits of statistical approaches with the adaptability and learning capabilities of ML models. The integration of selective ML techniques, such as anomaly detection or predictive analytics, into the statistical framework, may facilitate enhanced responsiveness to new threats while maintaining the security and efficiency benefits of the current model. Furthermore, the implementation of ongoing updates to the statistical model and the incorporation of feedback loops for continuous improvement could assist in mitigating some of the limitations identified in this analysis.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a novel approach to trust management in IoT environments, using a statistical Markov chain model and Multi-Attribute Decision-Making (MADM) methodology. Our implementation addressed key challenges in IoT trust management, including efficient resource utilisation, resilience to data sparsity and adaptability to diverse device types. The statistical approach is a viable alternative to traditional ML models, particularly in scenarios with restricted data. This protects ML-driven solutions from data poisoning and other forms of attack. The system's architectural components, including the TMS, IDS and DLT, form a comprehensive trust framework that reinforces the security of IoT networks. The method supports informed choices for IoT devices across different application domains. Despite the model's effectiveness in capturing dynamic trust relationships, the study acknowledges that handling emerging security threats requires further refinement.

The next step is to make the trust model more adaptable by responding to new threats. These could include zero-day vulnerabilities and use data from IDS and real-time threat intelligence. Alternative decision-making frameworks like fuzzy logic and Bayesian inference could improve our model's efficacy in addressing IoT network uncertainties. We will examine adversarial robustness, evaluate and mitigate vulnerabilities within the Markov chain framework, and perform a sensitivity analysis of the trust score model. These enhancements will reinforce the trust management framework, ensuring its scalability, resilience, and security across diverse IoT environments.

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